

LOCATING A NATIONAL COLLECTION REPORT

This report is based on surveys undertaken from May to July 2021 by volunteer teachers and their pupils respectively as a result of a blog (and the relevant links to Google Forms) posted on the Historical Association website. 164 pupils took part of whom 68.9% were female, 24.4% male; 6.7% designated themselves 'other' or preferred not to specify their gender. Geographically, they were predominantly located in London and the South-East (51.2%) and the South-West of England (45.7%) with a smattering from the North-East, North-West and East of England. Academically, the pupils ranged from Key Stage 2 to A level. 47 teachers responded to the survey drawn from a cross-section of schools both regionally and in terms of the type of school, though predominantly from Academies (48.9%) with a fair representation from Comprehensives (21%) and Independent senior schools (17%); some state primary and independent preparatory school teachers also took part. A small group of educators from both independent and state schools (senior and junior), who had taken part in the initial survey, agreed to participate in follow-up interviews in August and September 2021: 3 of these were in-depth held via Zoom (comprising a mixture of questions and structured discussion) and 2 were conducted via email.

Web provision

Levels of provision of technology in schools and access to web resources in the classroom varies. Although the majority of schools provide access to desktop computers, laptops or tablets or allow students to bring their own into the classroom, a significant proportion (44.7%) of schools either do not permit (for policy reasons) or do not have the resources to provide electronic devices for use in the classroom. Very few (8.5%) allow pupils to use their smartphones in class. Just under half of teachers surveyed expect pupils to use smartphones for doing work at home, although in fact only a fraction (4.3%) of the pupils surveyed use them for such work, preferring to use a laptop or tablet instead.

Three-quarters of the schools surveyed have not actively encouraged pupils to use online map interfaces to explore historical/cultural heritage sites and some teachers were not even aware of them. Teachers who did, however, would like their pupils to be able to source historical information about places and pictures of the place as it was in the past. A good proportion would also like to have links to pictures of the place as it is now or links to external sites with information about related places. Some teachers currently use Google Maps for this purpose. The ability to see what a place is like and garner links to associated places or collections that better inform an understanding of it has particular relevance for certain parts of the curriculum where they need to focus on a specific historical/heritage site or are encouraged to contextualise historical events on a local or regional basis.

This dovetails to a certain extent with pupils' own experiences. The majority (61.5%) use the internet to discover new things about history/heritage and particularly like finding out about historical films, dramas and novels. They are especially interested in stories linked to a particular heritage place (68.9%) and want to access pictures/videos of that place. While they are keen to find out more about the history of the place, they are slightly less concerned about other historical places with links to that place and what other resources

might be available. This suggests a disjunct between what their teachers would like them to do in the interests of their broader learning and what they actually focus on. Perhaps not surprisingly, a significant number (69.4%) of pupils prefer doing something relating to history/heritage in school time rather than out of school.

Teachers never set work where the pupils are just randomly searching (their learning is directed), but the pupils often ignore specific directions and look up on Wikipedia or sites that do not have academic reliability. Part of the skills being developed in researching is to refine searches and spot what is credible information and what not, but some pupils tend just to try and get the task done as quickly as possible. Although pupils are encouraged to search for information and sources, significant input from the teacher is still required in sourcing and preparing materials for the course. This additional research is usually employed to make individual lessons interesting. Websites of heritage/GLAM organisations (e.g. British Museum, British Library and National Archives and other museums) are used by teachers (and to a limited extent pupils), but provision of information needs to be tailored better to curriculum themes/topics and it is often difficult to navigate around some local organisations' websites. Some heritage organisations' websites seem educationally geared more towards primary school pupils rather than those at secondary level.

Visits to Heritage Sites

Visits offer a unique cultural experience and provide a memorable and tangible encounter with an historical place. This survey and interviews were undertaken during a period when the pandemic restrictions were in place or had only recently been lifted and so cannot give a perspective on subsequent attitudes, though it is apparent that visits to heritage sites have resumed. Engagement with cultural heritage (before lockdowns) was strong. Nearly a third of pupils said they visited throughout the year and almost two-thirds had visited a heritage site or museum once or twice a year with their family. Only a small proportion (7.3%) admitted they never go. There were not surprisingly slightly higher rates for teachers taking their families. In term time schools mostly visited once or twice a year, though nearly one fifth of pupils and 8.7% of teachers said that their school never undertake such visits. Those schools that did go on trips advised pupils to discover information about the place on-line before their visit. Interestingly, there was a marked preference among pupils for using guides and signs at the place rather than looking up on-line during or after a visit. This coincides to an extent with some schools' policy on pupils' use of mobile phones. measures. Some schools discourage or prohibit use of smart phones on school trips to sites to ensure they are concentrating on the task in hand or prevent misbehaviour. However, this obviously inhibits the ability to search websites or use any apps when on site.

Teachers who had undertaken visits generally had very positive feedback and found even just looking around and taking it all in increased pupils' enthusiasm for the subject. Understanding the physical heritage and the location heightened a sense of the emotive issues surrounding a place and improved their ability to make connections. Visiting the First World War battlefields, for instance, make them see the war in a different light. Seeing and handling objects/artefacts at sites was particularly useful.

Interest in Local History

Very few pupils (6%) are actively involved in groups or societies related to local heritage, but while nearly a third were uncommitted, a sizeable group (41.4%) expressed interest in the history of their local area. There were very positive responses from pupils to feeling part of their local communities. Nearly two-thirds (65.2%) agreed that where they lived was very special for them and they were proud of living there. Although they did not necessarily identify strongly with it, 81.1% had happy memories of the place. On the other hand, 70.2% of the teachers surveyed identified strongly with where they lived and 82.9% felt they were connected to the community.

There were very positive responses from pupils about their curiosity to find out more about the places they visit outside of their local area (63.4%). They were also keen on visiting historic buildings or museums when they visit other places in the UK (57.3%) and exploring the history of places they visit (59.7%). Not surprisingly the teachers surveyed registered a very strong interest in visiting and researching the history/heritage of other parts of the UK.

Teachers interviewed acknowledge the importance of situating a heritage site in its historical context, which can change substantially over time and incorporate different layers of history within it. The advantages of focusing on a local site has practical benefits in that it enables costs to be kept to a minimum and pupils can visit without taking too much time out of the school day. It also has educational value in enabling them to relate to something occurring in their own vicinity and to compare and contrast the local with the national scene. Where their own school (or its grounds) had historical features, teachers felt it increased a pupil's sense of belonging, especially to be able to use the history of the place they were learning in.

Relevance to Curriculum

An ability to use maps and search for both historical/heritage sites and sources related to those sites are skills that are embedded in a new focus at GCSE (Key Stage 4) on the historic environment and local history. There are now a number of public exam boards (e.g. aqa, edexcel, ocr/rsa) which incorporate these components as a specific module at GCSE. The exam boards have designed it themselves and so there are differences in the focus and the scope for any freedom of choice. One board concentrates on a specified building or location within a given historical timeframe: these cover Norman England (c.1066-1100), Medieval England (the Reign of Edward I, 1272-1307), Elizabethan England (1558-1603) and Restoration England (1660-85). Buildings can range from Castle Acre priory (Norfolk) or the White Tower (Tower of London) to the Merchant's House (Southampton) or Burleigh's Almshouse (Stamford, Lincs). The regional locations, which offer an alternative to a specific building, include Yorkshire after the Norman Conquest, Wales during Edward I's reign, or London Coffee Houses during the Restoration. The prescribed sites or areas change each year giving variety and opportunity for planned visits. There always seems to be a London-oriented and a northern based one.

Other boards are more thematic in their approach, concentrating on particular types of building (such as 'castles') and their location and function or particular environments through time (such as defined 'urban environments') and associated developments such as patterns of migration and the built environment. While specific examples are periodically specified (e.g. Kenilworth Castle and Spitalfields), there is scope for comparison with similar sites found locally. The thematic treatment of the historic environment by one exam board, however, is very broad, exploring changes and influences on 'medicine in Britain since 1250' or 'crime and punishment from c.1000'. This seems to provide more freedom of choice in the approach adopted by teachers. Although the general themes seem less geared towards specific locations regional examples of hospitals or prisons could be drawn upon.

There is no requirement for pupils to visit the sites, though the perspective afforded by the physical experience of an historical site is generally thought to be advantageous. The exam boards work with the heritage sites in providing certain course materials to assist with interpretation. There is an onus, however, on teachers/pupils locating sources of evidence themselves from maps and plans, local history collections, street names and oral histories as well as visible evidence of changes in building styles and their use.

This new turn towards the historical environment has ramifications for the earlier years and ought to stimulate engagement in the study of local history at Key Stages 2 and 3 in preparation for Key Stage 4. Ideally it should encourage and enable pupils to make connections between the place and local and national events and search local and national GLAM collections to provide sources to assist their interpretation. There is an element of cross-curriculum with an overlap between Key Stage 2 pupils' study of geography which involves making and using maps of their local area. This also corresponds with parallel geography and history field trips undertaken to heritage sites.

A level courses are more specialised in their examination of particular time periods and themes, but very much source based and source led. There is scope for a specific heritage-based focus in the extended essay. The subject could therefore be approached through images, objects and documents available on-line or in national and local collections.

Challenges

While some schools are extremely well-equipped, others struggle to provide web access and recent reports have highlighted 'Digital Poverty' and problems in certain schools with provision of computers or sufficient for meaningful use in classroom/homework situation.

Heritage organisations are generally more pro-active in working with schools (particularly those local to them). School visits to heritage sites/museums are increasingly hidebound by red tape and bureaucracy (both the organisation's and school's own). The biggest drawback to undertaking visits seems to be the practical aspects of organising getting there and the endless paperwork and risk assessments for busy teachers to carry out and trying to fit in visits with school timetable.

Head teachers need to be convinced of the educational value of visits to heritage sites (time spent out of school privileging one subject over others) and this has to be balanced against costs of trips (unless very local) and other priorities. Planning visits in conjunction with other subjects can be

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Recommendations

There are advantages for heritage sites/GLAM organisations in having awareness of different learning stages and ensuring alignment with topics on curriculum, particularly at GCSE and A level.

Heritage and GLAM organisations should work pro-actively with schools/exam boards in promoting collections and linking web resources.

Heritage sites/GLAM organisations should be encouraged to promote interactive activities on their websites that involve discovery and use of sources to solve problems (akin to a game) – suitable for specific topics/research projects.

In relation to LaNC website:

- themed maps and timelines coinciding with the syllabus requirements so that educators/pupils can see which sites or artefacts are of relevance quickly.
- Local searches through history pin useful if can identify what resources/places to visit for particular period.
- Links to 'lost' buildings/environments and where maps/plans and recreations available.

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